

Modeling Project: AI Event Website

The xyz (name of the group/university is not provided due to anonymity) group wants to develop a dedicated website to centralize and promote all upcoming AI-related events, initiatives, and discussion forums. The website will serve as a comprehensive resource for students, faculty, and researchers interested in AI, offering essential information on department-organized events and conferences as well as relevant external events that may appeal to the academic community. In addition, the platform will feature a communication channel where department members can post AI-related content and engage in discussions, fostering an active community centered around AI topics.

The website must meet departmental standards for data accuracy and adhere to university policies regarding content management and user interaction.

Phase 1: Requirement Elicitation

To achieve this, students will interact with two key stakeholders:

1. Product Owner : A representative from the university administration who will provide insights into the website's objectives, core functionalities, and compliance requirements, ensuring that the final product aligns with institutional goals and policies.
2. Domain Expert: A professor specializing in AI, who will offer a deep understanding of the field, potential user needs, and specific requirements that enhance the platform's relevance and value for AI-focused users.

Each student will have a **15-minute** session with both the product owner and the domain expert, respectively.

Duration: 30 mins + 10 minutes to prioritize and write down the requirements.

Outcome of Phase 1: A Prioritized Requirements List – a comprehensive document listing the gathered requirements, organized by priority based on stakeholder input.

Phase 2: Modeling

Students will get 20 minutes to make a UML-based plan that models the domain, core functionalities, and structure of the website for the product owner. Apart from domain model, students can select two functionalities to demonstrate through UML diagrams, showcasing the website's main features and user interactions.

Duration: 20 minutes

Outcome of Phase 2: A UML-based representation that captures:

- The domain: students must mention the different parts of the domain, what is inside the system and what's outside. Students can use class diagrams for it. **Please note that** students don't have to create the diagram but must mention the different entities present in the domain so that the product owner gets an overview of the website.
- At least two functionalities (from their prioritized list of requirements) and suitable UML behavioral diagrams to model them. **Please note that**, students must create the diagrams and also explain why they have selected that particular diagram type to model such functionality to the product owner.

Initial questions to ask the product owner

1. What are the core goals you hope this website will achieve for the department and its members?
2. Who are the main users of the website?
3. What specific information or features do you think each user group will need?
4. What type of communication features would you like for the discussion platform? Should it support real-time chat, threaded discussions, or perhaps both?

Afterwards, students are free to interact with the product owner in their own way.

Initial questions to ask the domain expert

1. What types of AI-related content and events do you think are most valuable for students and faculty to stay updated on?
2. What policies or standards should we follow to ensure that the information on AI topics and events is accurate and up-to-date?
3. Are there specific tools or platforms commonly used in the AI research community that we should consider integrating or linking to on the website?
4. What ethical or privacy considerations should we keep in mind when publishing AI research discussions or sharing event information publicly?

Afterwards, students are free to interact with the product owner in their own way.

